

HISTORICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL CRAFTS IN UZBEKISTAN

Meliboyeva Sarvinoz

Kokand State University

Senior Lecturer, PhD

ANNOTATION: This article analyzes the historical and pedagogical foundations of the development of national crafts in Uzbekistan. The stages of the formation of national crafts, their role in the material and spiritual culture of the people, and their importance in the education of the younger generation are highlighted. The role of the teacher-student system in passing on craft traditions from generation to generation, and its pedagogical possibilities in preserving and developing national values are also revealed. The article analyzes the state policy aimed at supporting national crafts during the years of independence and its results, and provides scientific conclusions and recommendations on the effective use of craft heritage in the educational process.

KEYWORDS: national crafts, folk applied arts, historical and pedagogical foundations, master-student tradition, national values, spiritual education, cultural heritage, vocational education, craft schools, youth education, pedagogical opportunities, innovative approaches.

INTRODUCTION

National crafts are an integral part of the material and spiritual culture of the people, formed over the centuries. It is not only a type of economic activity, but also a unique cultural heritage that embodies the lifestyle, aesthetic views, labor traditions and spiritual values of the people. Since ancient times, such crafts as

pottery, jewelry, embroidery, coppersmithing, woodcarving, carpet weaving, weaving have developed on the territory of Uzbekistan and have occupied an important place in the life of the people. Archaeological finds, historical sources and ethnographic studies confirm that crafts in this region have a history of several thousand years.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Uzbekistan, one of the ancient trade and cultural centers of Central Asia, was located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road, which provided favorable conditions for the development of various areas of craftsmanship. Cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Kokand, Margilan, Rishton, and Shahrisabz were famous not only as trading centers, but also as hotbeds of the formation and development of craft schools. The products created in these centers were recognized in different countries of the world for their elegance, durability, and artistic value.

The development of crafts is closely related to the development of society, and it has served as an important means of transmitting the labor experience, worldview and aesthetic taste of the people from generation to generation. In particular, the tradition of master-discipleship has acquired historical significance as an effective mechanism for preserving the secrets of crafts and teaching them to the younger generation. Through this system, not only professional skills were formed, but also such human qualities as diligence, patience, responsibility, patriotism and respect for national values.

In today's globalization environment, preserving the national cultural heritage, instilling it in the minds of the younger generation, and developing it in line with modern requirements are urgent issues. In recent years, our country has been implementing large-scale reforms aimed at supporting national crafts, encouraging the activities of craftsmen, promoting examples of folk applied art, and integrating crafts with the education system. This requires a deep study of not only the

economic, but also pedagogical and educational potential of crafts.

From a pedagogical point of view, national crafts are one of the important factors in developing the creative abilities of young people, providing them with professional guidance, awareness of national identity, and spiritual maturity. Craft activities, along with the formation of practical skills in students, serve to develop aesthetic taste, creative thinking, independent thinking, and labor culture. Therefore, a scientific analysis of the historical development of crafts and its pedagogical potential is considered one of the important tasks facing modern education.

RESULTS

This article analyzes the stages of formation and development of national crafts in Uzbekistan, its historical roots, traditions of master-student, and pedagogical significance in the upbringing of the younger generation. It also highlights the historical and pedagogical foundations of the development of national crafts and the possibilities of their application in educational practice.

Regardless of its direction and purpose, any, in particular, educational and upbringing activity is organized in accordance with legal and organizational-pedagogical foundations. Pedagogical activity that aims to direct adolescents to a profession, develop in them primary professional knowledge, skills, qualifications, experience and their aggregate competencies, and also pursues a specific goal, is not launched by chance or simply. Rather, it is organized in accordance with a strategic approach, conceptually well-thought-out, with a rationally constructed implementation mechanism.

Determining a clear trajectory of activity in the pedagogical direction, developing a roadmap for its consistent, step-by-step, dynamic organization is carried out taking into account the social order that society places before educational institutions, as well as the spiritual needs of the subjects. In a word, the pedagogical process, based on the principle of "unity of society and personality", is based on

integration with the development of the relevant social sphere. Therefore, at the same time, increasing the social significance of national crafts in the Republic of Uzbekistan, further developing crafts concentrated on the platform of folk production, focusing on the prospects for the development of tourism, which plays an important role in the economy of society, is one of the most important social tasks facing society.

DISCUSSION

Crafts have been developed since ancient times. According to the Holy Quran, the sacred source of Islamic teachings, almost all of the prophets earned their living through one profession or another. In particular, Adam (peace be upon him) and Job were farmers, Noah and Zechariah were carpenters, Idris was a physician, Hud, Salih and Muhammad (peace be upon them) were merchants, Abraham was a farmer, Ishmael and Jesus were hunters, Dhulkifli was a baker, Isaac, Jacob, Shuaib and Moses were shepherds, Joseph was a watchmaker, and Jonah was a fisherman. A group of prophets were directly involved in crafts. For example, the prophets Idris and Elijah were engaged in sewing and weaving, and the prophets David and Solomon were engaged in blacksmithing.

A group of prophets had two professions or trades. For example, Prophet Salih was also a builder, Prophet Solomon was a basket maker, Prophet Jesus was a shepherd, and Muhammad (pbuh) was a shepherd (shepherd, in his youth).

Therefore, the fact that the prophets Noah and Zechariah were carpenters, the prophets Idris and Elijah were tailors and weavers, and the prophets David and Solomon were blacksmiths in their time indicates that they also earned a reputation as craftsmen.

The initial information about crafts, types of crafts, socio-cultural significance, and their place in the way of life of the people are found in sources of various nations, including the “Laws of Manu”, “Ramayana”, “Mahabhorat”

(ancient India), “Advice to Merikaru, the son of the king of Herakleopolis”, “Proverbs of Ipusera” (ancient Egypt), the teachings of “Guan-Tsi” (“Reed-like scroll”) (ancient China), “Avesta”, “Devonu-lu'otit Turk” (Mahmud Kashgari), “O'gitlar” (Muhammad al-Khwarizmi), “Minerology” (Abu Rayhan Beruni), “Achievement of Happiness”, “City of Virtuous People” (Abu Nasr al-Farabi), “Qutadgu bilig” (Yusuf Khos Hajib), “Hibat-ul-haqoyikq” (Ahmad Yugnaki), “As-sahih” (Ismail al-Bukhari), “Qobusnama” (Kaykovus), “Rubaiylar” (Pahlavon Mahmud), “Gul and Navruz” (Lutfi), “Khamsa”, “Mahbub-ul-qulub” (Alisher Navoi), “Majma'ul navodir” (“Rare Stories”; Nizami Aro'zi Samarkandi), “Baburnama” (Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur) and other works.

The history of the development of crafts dates back to the earliest periods of human development. In the early stages of social civilization, the first manifestations of human labor activity aimed at eating, drinking, dressing, and gathering directly paved the way for the formation of the first foundations of crafts. Initially, all people engaged in agriculture or animal husbandry tried to satisfy their own needs for eating, drinking, dressing, and gathering. However, the increase in the scale of work, the increase in the number of livestock, the increase in the size of cultivated land, the diversity of crop types, and the increasing demand for their care led to the emergence of a certain category of people among farmers and animal husbandry. It was thanks to their labor that the household needs of farmers and animal husbandry, consisting of household goods, household appliances, and clothing, began to be consistently, constantly, and continuously satisfied.

The availability of natural resources in the region served as a key factor for the development of certain crafts in different places. The basics of processing existing raw materials, naturally, have constantly made people living in the region think about them, and they have paid attention to the effective use of resources. For example, the territory of the current Rishton district has fertile soil from a

geographical point of view, which is why pottery has developed there. Since reed plants grow a lot in swampy areas, basketry and weaving from it have become popular there. Textiles have developed in areas where livestock (wool, leather), cotton, cocoons are grown. In areas where it is easy to find fabrics such as silk, satin, and velvet, headgear has flourished. In areas where mulberry and willow trees are grown, an important branch of woodworking - cradle making - has been widely developed.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Craftsmanship is considered a dynastic activity. Usually, a person who worked in a particular craft taught its secrets, first of all, to his children and relatives, and then took on children and adolescents living in nearby and then distant regions as apprentices. Therefore, craftsmen have centuries-old traditions.

"As early as the first centuries of our era, people realized that ganch has wonderful properties and began to use it to decorate fortresses, caravanserais and other places. As a result of the battles that took place, they were destroyed, and only their remains have survived. In the 3rd century, the luxurious palace hotels of Tuproqkala were decorated with ganch, and among the finds in Varakhsha, samples were found from the remains of the Bukhara palace of the 7th-8th centuries. On these samples, one can see carved patterns of birds, animals, fish, plant and geometric shapes."

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2021. – 464 b.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Erkin va farovon, demokratik O'zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2017. – 56 b.
3. Karimov I.A. Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch. – Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 2008. – 176 b.

4. Bulatov S.S. O‘zbek xalq amaliy bezak san’ati. – Toshkent: Mehnat, 1991. – 384 b.
5. Bulatov S.S. Amaliy san’at qisqacha lug‘ati. – Toshkent: Qomuslar bosh tahririyati, 1992. – 168 b.
6. Pugachenkova G.A., Rempel L.I. Ocherki iskusstva Sredney Azii. – Moskva: Iskustvo, 1982. – 288 s.
7. Azimova B. O‘zbekiston amaliy san’ati tarixi. – Toshkent: Fan, 2009. – 256 b.
8. Xakimov A.A. O‘zbekiston san’ati tarixi. – Toshkent: Sharq, 2010. – 320 b.
9. Jabborov I. O‘zbek xalq etnografiyasi. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 1994. – 280 b.
10. Rasulov M. Xalq hunarmandchiligi va badiiy meros. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2016. – 224 b.
11. Abduqodirov A.A. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va ta’lim innovatsiyalari. – Toshkent: Fan, 2019. – 240 b.
12. Musurmonova O. Oila ma’naviyati va yoshlar tarbiyasi. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 2018. – 196 b.
13. Tolipov O‘.Q., Usmonboyeva M. Pedagogik texnologiyalarning tatbiqiy asoslari. – Toshkent: Fan, 2006. – 260 b.
14. Ochilov M. Yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar. – Qarshi: Nasaf, 2000. – 182 b.
15. Nishonova S. Pedagogika tarixi. – Toshkent: O‘qituvchi, 2012. – 312 b.
16. Hasanboyev J., To‘raqulov X., Haydarov M. Pedagogika. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2011. – 480 b.
17. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining hunarmandchilik faoliyatini qo‘llab-quvvatlashga oid farmon va qarorlari to‘plami. – Toshkent, 2019.

18. “Hunarmand” uyushmasi faoliyatiga oid me’yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlar to‘plami. – Toshkent, 2022.

19. UNESCO. Traditional Craftsmanship and Intangible Cultural Heritage. – Paris: UNESCO Publishing, 2020. – 145 p.

20. O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi. 12 jildlik. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2000–2006.

21. Feruza Aminovna Turakulova. Free Time of Students in Qualification Practicecontent Organization Technology. Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress (JARSP) Volume: 02 Issue: 10 | 2023 ISSN: 2751-7551 <http://innosci.org/>